

Supplementary Document

Experiments setup and evaluation protocols

This document complements the manuscript **Microsoft HoloLens 2 vs. Tablet-based Augmented Reality and 3D printing for fronto-orbital reconstruction of craniosynostosis: A case study**. This document details the protocols followed for evaluating the proposed systems, both in the simulation scenario and during surgery. This work has been developed by Alicia Pose Díez de la Lastra, Mónica García Sevilla, Austin Tapp, Manuel Tousidonis, Juan Vicente Darriba Alles, Marius George Lingurar, Javier Pascau, and Santiago Ochandiano and published in the journal 3D Printing in Medicine. Please read the main manuscript before this document.

1. Surface scanning

To evaluate and compare the efficiency of bone placement guidance using the three guidance methods (3D-printed spacers, AR on a tablet, and AR on Microsoft HoloLens 2), we employed an Artec Eva (Artec3D, Senningerber, Luxembourg) structured light scanner. The device's 3D resolution, according to the manufacturer, is 0.2 mm [1]. Furthermore, we validated its accuracy in this context in previous work, where we registered the surface of a bone scanned with both the Artec Eva and a CT scanner, obtaining a mean deviation error of 0.3 mm between the two surfaces [2]. This solution is, therefore, not only sufficiently accurate to serve as a gold standard for system evaluation but also eliminates the need for additional CT scans, thereby sparing the patient an extra dose of ionizing radiation.

After adjusting a bone fragment using each method, we acquired 3D scans of the resulting configuration. Using Artec Studio 18 professional software [3] we generated 3D models from the scans and exported them in OBJ format for the geometric data, along with a BMP file for texture information. Both files were then imported into 3D Slicer for a colored visualization of the 3D model.

2. Simulation scenario

2.1. 3D-printed patient-specific phantoms design

Prior to the surgery, we conducted experiments in a simulation scenario using 3D-printed patient-based phantoms. The main phantom consisted of the patient's skull without the SO bar and the frontal bone, with the AR guides in place (Figure 1A). Two additional phantoms, independently representing the remodeled SO bar and the frontal bone, were also created (Figure 1B and C, respectively). All phantoms were based on original models extracted from the virtual surgical plan (VSP) but were modified by adding several 8×8 mm squares on their surfaces: four on the skull and the frontal bone, and three on the SO bar. The squares were yellow on the skull phantom and red on the frontal bone and SO bar phantoms. These squares were used as registration markers to analyze each system's performance during the phantom experiments. The phantoms were 3D printed with polylactic acid (PLA) in two colors using the fused deposition modeling (FDM) technique on a double extruder Raise 3D Pro 2 3D printer.

Figure 1. Virtual design of the patient-specific phantoms of the (A) skull, (B) SO bar and (C) frontal bone for the experimentation in the simulation scenario.

2.2. Performance evaluation: Simulation scenario

We achieved semiautomatic registration of the scanned models with the VSP by utilizing the color information associated with each point in the mesh of the former. The RGB (red, green, blue) color values were converted to HSV (hue, saturation, value) format, and a range for hue and saturation was manually selected to isolate the yellow points in the mesh. The K-means algorithm was then applied to classify these points into four clusters, corresponding to the four 8×8 mm yellow squares on the skull phantom. By calculating the centroid of each cluster, we registered the squares in the scanned model to their counterparts in the VSP using a point-based registration algorithm. After registering the scanned skull to the reference skull, we repeated the process to identify the center points of the red squares on the SO bar or frontal bone in the scanned model. The misalignment of these points relative to those in the VSP indicates the accuracy of bone fragment placement, thus reflecting the effectiveness of each guidance method. This methodology is based on that presented in [4].

Before using this protocol to semi-automatically evaluate the results in the simulation scenario, we validated its reliability. We acquired five scans of the skull phantom, generated the corresponding 3D models, and registered them pairwise using the described

methodology. The intrinsic error of the protocol was determined by calculating the root mean square error (RMSE) from the pairwise registrations of the five scans, which averaged 0.4 ± 0.1 mm. The results for bone placement accuracy in the simulation scenario are presented in the main manuscript.

3. Surgical scenario

3.1. Surgical experience

The complete surgical experience is summarized in Figure 2, separated by the steps schematized in Figure 1 of the main manuscript. The placement of the remodeled SO bar bone was initially guided by the 3D-printed spacers, which were inserted into the SO bar gap. After scanning the result, the spacers were removed. Next, a nurse assisted the surgeon in enclosing the tablet in a sterile eShield cover designed for surgical use [5]. The AR markers, already fitted in the AR guides, were quickly recognized by the AR application, which overlaid the virtual information onto the patient. Due to the positioning of the AR markers on the head, the surgeon had to move around the patient multiple times, aligning the real SO bar with its virtual counterpart from both the left and right sides. Surgical clamps were used to hold one side of the SO bar in place while the other side was adjusted using the AR display. These clamps were also employed to secure the SO bar during the subsequent surface scan. After this, the SO bar was removed again.

To finish, the tablet was put aside, and a nurse placed the Microsoft HoloLens 2 on the surgeon's head. The AR markers were recognized almost instantly, displaying the virtual information correctly. Simultaneously, another surgeon wore a second Microsoft HoloLens 2 running the same application. To reposition the SO bar using this method, each surgeon

focused on one marker at a time and adjusted the SO bar from their respective sides. Although the applications on the two devices were not synchronized, they independently displayed the ideal position of the SO bar from their perspective, eliminating the need to move around the patient.

Figure 2. Surgical workflow followed during the actual surgery, with the steps schematized in Figure 1 of the main manuscript.

While the placement of the SO bar with the three methods could be successfully recorded for further evaluation, time constraints prevented the same process from being applied to the frontal bone. As a result, the neurosurgeons placed the frontal bone using traditional methods and anatomical references. Nonetheless, after placement, the final position of the frontal bone was verified with the virtual visualization provided by the tablet application.

3.2. Performance evaluation: Surgical scenario

The surgery was performed seven and a half weeks after the CT scan was acquired, resulting in a slight increase in the patient's head size from the original plan to the final appearance in the surgical room. Although this growth was not significant enough to necessitate a new surgical plan, it was considered during the analysis of the results. As such, a structured light scan of the exposed cranium was acquired after step 1 of the surgery (Figure 1 in the main manuscript), and the visible bone surface was registered to the original CT scan, obtaining a scaling factor of 0.98. This scaling factor was then applied to all subsequent scans before analyzing bone placement accuracy in the surgical scenario.

For the following analysis, since color markers could not be used to register the scanned models to the VSP, an alternative protocol was implemented. To register the scaled scan to the VSP, we manually placed eight fiducials on identifiable landmarks on the AR markers (four per marker) and aligned them with their corresponding points in the ideal plan using point-based registration. Following this, the registration was refined by aligning the surfaces of the AR marker pairs using the Model Registration module in 3D Slicer. Then, a model of the ideal bone fragment under evaluation was aligned with the bone fragment in the scan

using surface registration algorithms. The placement accuracy of that bone fragment was defined as the difference in pose between the virtual bone fragment in the scanned position and in the VSP.

We adopted this approach because the surface scanner can smooth the bone fragment's edges and slightly distort its shape. Therefore, directly comparing the scanned bone to the ideal bone could introduce errors in the distance map unrelated to the actual placement but to the shape. Aligning the ideal fragment to the scanned fragment and then comparing its pose to that in the VSP guarantees that only the differences in position are quantified.

4. Rotation error by axes

Table 1 collects the mean translation and rotation errors obtained for each bone, scenario, and guidance method, broken down by axis.

Table 1. Mean translation and rotation errors obtained for each bone, scenario, and guidance method, broken down by axis.

			Mean translation error by axis \pm std (mm), in absolute value			Mean rotation error by axis \pm std ($^{\circ}$), in absolute value		
			R	A	S	R	A	S
SO bar	Surgical scenario*	Tablet	0.1	1.4	0.2	0.5	0.5	1.5
		HL2	1.0	1.0	0.3	0.3	0.9	1.3
		Spacers	0.1	0.4	0.1	1.5	1.4	0.2
	Simulation scenario	Tablet	0.9 ± 0.5	0.5 ± 0.3	0.5 ± 0.3	1.0 ± 0.4	0.1 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1
		HL2	1.0 ± 0.4	0.6 ± 0.4	0.4 ± 0.2	1.2 ± 1.0	0.3 ± 0.3	0.3 ± 0.3
		Spacers	0.5 ± 0.5	0.8 ± 0.3	0.4 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.8	0.1 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.2
Frontal bone	Tablet	0.4 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.3	0.9 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.7	0.5 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.5	
	HL2	0.4 ± 0.3	0.5 ± 0.5	0.9 ± 0.2	1.5 ± 0.5	0.5 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.6	

* A single user (the surgeon) performed this experiment. Therefore, standard deviation metrics are not applicable in this case.

5. Specifications of equipment and consumables employed

The specifications of the equipment and consumables used in the development of this work are listed below.

- Equipment:
 - Artec Eva 3D surface scanner
 - Tablet Samsung Galaxy Tab S7 FE
 - Raise 3D Pro 2 3D printer – For AR markers, in PLA
 - Formlabs Form 2 3D printer – For AR guides, in resin
 - EOS 3D printer – For surgical guides and templates, in PA12
- Software:
 - Artec Studio 18 professional
 - 3D Slicer 5.6.2.
 - Unity 2022.3.20f1
- 3D printing materials
 - PLA (polylactic acid)
 - BioMed Clear V1 resin
 - PA12 (polyamide 12)

References

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